

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

USING FIGMA TO DEVELOP CREATIVITY IN BACHELORS OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

Figma is a robust cloud-based graphical interface design tool that is becoming indispensable in training IT professionals. It allows students to acquire technical skills and develop creativity, crucial for competitiveness in the modern labour market. Integrating Figma into the educational process provides future IT professionals with tools for working with prototypes and design. It allows them to work on team projects in real time, bringing students closer to real-world design conditions.

Unlike traditional tools, Figma offers a cloud-based environment where students can create and edit interfaces from any device, providing easy access and flexibility in learning. This is particularly useful in a distance learning environment where students can collaborate on assignments using collaborative editing, commenting and interactive prototyping functionality. Figma actively promotes the development of creative competencies, stimulates divergent thinking through prototyping tools, and facilitates teamwork and idea sharing. Its rich plugin templates provide students with additional opportunities to create unique solutions. Hands-on learning of Figma tools in courses such as Computer Graphics and GUI Design allows students to gain practical experience and creative problem-solving skills, which is extremely valuable for future employment.

Keywords: creativity, Figma, interface design, computer graphics, creativity developing.

INTRODUCTION

Every year, higher education institutions' educational and professional programmes undergo constant changes to meet the challenges of time and labour market demands. In the rapid development of information technology, it is important to integrate modern tools and software into the educational process to train highly qualified specialists. In IT education, it is important to provide students with access to innovative solutions that allow them to develop their professional competencies and creative approaches to solving technical problems.

One such tool is Figma, a cloud-based service for designing graphical interfaces. Figma allows students to work on creating graphical interfaces for computer games, web applications, and mobile devices, allowing them to gain the practical experience they need to work on real-world projects.

One of Figma's key advantages is its intuitive functionality, actively promoting students' creativity. Students can create modern, high-quality solutions in building interfaces thanks to many tools. In addition, Figma supports using numerous plugins to automate processes, work with typography and colour schemes, and import ready-made components from external resources.

Figma also provides real-time collaboration capabilities that allow students to develop teamwork, share ideas, and quickly change their projects. This combination stimulates active discussion of design solutions, promoting critical thinking and openness to new approaches.

As part of the Computer Graphics and Graphical Interface Design course, students use this tool to complete laboratory assignments, which helps develop their creativity. While working at Figma, students not only learn new technical skills but also learn to solve their tasks innovatively. Using Figma's interactive features allows you to work in conditions close to the actual design process, which forms the readiness of students to work on projects after graduation.

This article studies the use of the service for building Figma interfaces to develop creativity in information technology students.

This study aims to discover how integrating Figma into IT education contributes to developing creative thinking in information technology bachelor's students.

The study's novelty lies in developing a new methodological approach to integrating cloud-based design tools (Figma, for example) into IT education. This approach consists of obtaining results on the relationship

between using this tool and developing creative competencies.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Vatsal Sharma and Ankit Kumar Tiwari Studied User Interface and User Experience Designs and their Tools [1] and pointed out the importance of UI/UX (User Interface/User Experience) in the modern world of technology and design. The authors reveal the basic UI/UX design concepts and their importance for users and analyse the primary tools used to create interfaces, including Figma, Adobe XD, and Sketch. The article also describes the impact of a well-designed UI architecture on the interaction between the user and the product, in particular through visual and functional design aspects.

In the article, the authors conclude that UI/UX is an important component of creating quality products, and appropriate tools and technologies can significantly improve the user experience. However, to achieve success, it is necessary to properly divide responsibilities between designers and developers so everyone can perform their role as efficiently as possible. The authors also emphasise the need to constantly update knowledge in the field of UI/UX due to the rapid development of technologies such as artificial intelligence and natural interfaces [1].

The article by Miftah Faroq Santoso (2024) notes that web design and application interface development should focus on visual aesthetics, usability, and user experience (UX). The authors discuss the importance of harmonising user interface (UI) elements, colour schemes, typography, and element layout and simplifying the interaction with applications to provide a better user experience. The paper highlights the importance of integrating UI/UX principles into website and application design. It also emphasises the importance of using tools like Figma to build and test interfaces. Thus, the authors conclude that well-designed interfaces directly impact user satisfaction and, consequently, the success of an application or website [2].

The article by Yanfi Yanfi and Pualam Dipa Nusantara explores the user interface UI design and user experience UX for a mobile application. The focus is prototyping a community app for a non-profit organisation using the Marvel tool for UI design. A task-oriented design method is used, including user identification and analysis of their needs. The prototype is also evaluated using a USE questionnaire to measure usefulness, ease of use, learning, and satisfaction. The results showed a high level of user acceptance. The article's authors also note that UI and UX design are effective solutions for non-profit organisations' applications, allowing them to meet users' needs better [3].

The article by Tang Tang, Valentina Vezzani, and Vikki Eriksson explores the connection between creativity and critical thinking and their implications for the educational process. It aims to understand how these two skills are interrelated and how they can be simultaneously developed within a learning framework. The study involves analysing student performance on creativity and critical thinking assessments alongside examining teaching strategies that foster these abilities. The findings suggest that creativity and critical thinking are

complementary skills essential for problem-solving and academic success. The authors emphasise that interactive teaching methods, such as project-based learning and digital tools, significantly enhance the development of these competencies [4].

Authors Yoed N. Kenett, David J.M. Kraemer, Katherine L. Alfred, Griffin A. Colaizzi, Robert A. Cortes, and Adam E. Green explore the challenges in standardising creativity measurement methods and propose a new approach to address them. The authors use meta-analytical tools like the NeuroSynth software to create maps of neural activity associated with various creativity tasks. Using representation similarity analysis (RSA), they determine which tasks most accurately reflect different aspects of creativity. This approach helps to identify optimal sets of tasks for assessing creativity and can significantly advance research in this area [5].

Hansika Kapoor, Tim Patston, David H. Croypley, Sarah Rezai, and James Kaufman studied the relationship between creativity and academic achievement. They found that creativity is a significant predictor of standardised educational test scores. This underscores the importance of developing students' creativity to achieve higher academic performance [6].

The article by Ji Eun Min and Byung-Kyung Kim explores the relationship between creativity and productivity in collaborations between artists and STEM professionals. The study examines antecedent factors that influence creativity between these groups and details the outcomes of temporary and imperfect organisational creativity. A survey was conducted among 969 Korean artists and STEM professionals, and data from 131 respondents with experience in arts and STEM collaboration were analysed using a structural equation model. The results indicate that intrinsic motivation and creative personality characteristics positively impact creativity-mediated collaboration. This research deepens the understanding of creativity and collaboration between artists and STEM professionals, especially in temporary and imperfect organisational settings, confirming that the coexistence of scientific and artistic creativity positively impacts collaboration [7].

A study by Ophelia A. Desmet and Robert J. Sternberg highlights the importance of developing transformational creativity in students to drive positive social change.

The authors propose several strategies for educators:

1. Creating creativity-friendly classrooms: Creating an environment encouraging risk-taking and diverse thinking.
2. Implementing holistic education: Integrating different disciplines to provide a holistic learning experience.
3. Incorporating care, empathy and ethics: Embedding these values in creative projects so that innovation benefits society.
4. Assessment of transformational creativity: Using special rubrics and portfolios to assess students' creative progress.

By applying these approaches, educators can develop students' abilities to generate innovative solutions that contribute to a just and sustainable future [7].

The impact of education based on creative problem-solving and asynchronous online discussions on student creativity in a product design course is explored by Yi-Chia Tsai and Fu-Song Hsu. This study examines how integrating creative problem-solving (CPS) methodologies with asynchronous online discussions affects student creativity in a product design curriculum. The results of the study show that this combined educational approach significantly enhances students' creativity, offering valuable insights for educators seeking to foster creativity in design education [8].

Peiyao Chen and Tongwei Liu studied the effectiveness of a cognitive-oriented creativity training programme designed for school-age children. The researchers conducted pre-, post-, and control tests to compare the results of two groups matched for working memory at the pre-test stage. One group (n = 33) participated in the training programme, while the control group (n = 27) studied in an active control condition. The results showed that the training group demonstrated significantly better creative thinking scores than the control group on the post-test. Notably, this improvement was maintained for six months and did not depend on changes in working memory. In addition, participants with lower baseline creative thinking scores benefited more from the training than those with higher baseline scores. These findings suggest that cognitive creativity training can effectively develop and maintain learners' creative thinking skills, especially for those who start with low levels of creativity [8].

The study of the impact of creative educational modules combined with the methods of cognitive research trust (CoRT) and problem-based learning (PBL) on students' skills and perception of scientific creativity is presented by C. Bulut Ates and H. Aktamis. This study examines how integrating CoRT methods with PBL affects students' scientific creativity and perceptions of learning. The results show that this blended educational approach significantly improves students' creative thinking behaviour, which indicates its effectiveness in developing scientific creativity in the educational environment [9].

In their scientific work, Merav Deshome, Maxence Mercier, Cyril Fabesse, Todd Lubart, Gael Chouvelon, Solenn Kermarrek and Sylvie Tordjman examine the relationship between intelligence and creativity. The study analyses convergent and divergent thought processes to determine whether intelligence is necessary and sufficient for creativity. The study's results suggest that although intelligence plays a significant role in creative thinking, it may not be the only factor that indicates the involvement of other cognitive and environmental elements in the creative process [10].

METHODOLOGY

The research employed a mixed-method approach combining quantitative and qualitative methodologies through an experimental design. The study was conducted during one semester in the Computer Graphics and Graphical Interface Design course at Zhytomyr

Polytechnic State University. It involved 130 second-year IT students divided into experimental (EG) and control (CG) groups of 65 students each.

The data collection process incorporated multiple assessment methods to evaluate creative skills development and academic achievement. The initial creativity assessment was conducted through four computer graphics works serving as a pre-test, while the final evaluation involved project presentations that were assessed based on originality, flexibility, productivity, and detail. Academic achievement was measured using a four-level grading scale ranging from primary (1-59 points) to high (90-100 points), with intermediate (60-73 points) and sufficient (74-89 points) levels in between.

Teacher observations during laboratory sessions provided qualitative data on student participation in brainstorming sessions, team activities, project presentations, and creative problem-solving tasks. The observational data complemented the quantitative measurements, offering insights into the development of creative thinking and collaborative skills.

Data analysis combined quantitative and qualitative approaches. Quantitative analysis utilised Pearson's χ^2 test to determine statistical significance between the experimental and control groups. Qualitative analysis focused on assessing creative output quality, project originality, and student approaches to problem-solving.

Research Questions (RQs) of our study are:

RQ1: How does the integration of Figma in the educational process influence the development of creativity among bachelor's degree students in information technology?

RQ2: How does the collaborative nature of Figma's cloud-based environment impact students' creative problem-solving abilities and team-based learning?

Hypotheses of our research are:

H1: The integration of Figma in IT education significantly enhances students' creative thinking abilities as measured by originality, flexibility, productivity, and detail in their project work.

RESULTS

When training for a bachelor's degree in Computer Science, the educational and professional program (*Computer Graphics and Game Development*, 2024) provides several graphic editors in different directions. Among them is Figma, an editor who designs interfaces for mobile and web applications. Figma is a cloud-based service that interface designers actively use. The service's functionality allows you to create lo-fi and hi-fi wireframes, develop UI Kits, and adapt them to various projects. Among many similar products on the market, one of the most significant advantages of Figma is the ability to prototype in real-time, forming a workable user flow and testing it in building an architecture. The convenience of using Figma lies in the fact that the service covers the entire set of tools necessary for the work of a UI/UX designer. The cloud-based service allows brainstorming, developing lo-fi and lo-hi mockups, customising user flow, generating CSS, iOS, and Android code, and supporting teamwork on the project.

Figma has an intuitive interface as a computer graphics development service. The environment is di-

vided into three modes of operation: design, prototyping, and developer mode, which is available with a premium subscription (see Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Figma workspace

Source: Figma (<https://www.figma.com>)

An important advantage of using Figma for students is the ability to use the Figma Community. The Figma Community platform contains additional components that can be used in your projects. UI Kits, Wireframes, Design Templates, and various plugins significantly speed up the work and improve the design quality [11].

This platform is studied step by step. In the first classes, students are offered introductory tasks that involve creating a new project and working with frames and screen extensions. As part of the laboratory assignments, students are encouraged to learn how to work with text blocks, their designs, and forms and icons. Students are given practical knowledge of working with modular grids, which will become integral to the interface design process in future projects.

Studying the discipline and mastering Figma involves developing students' general competencies, such as thinking abstractly, analysing and synthesising, generating new ideas (creativity), etc.

Teaching IT students to use computer graphics helps to form and develop creativity. Creativity is the ability to create new ideas, solutions, and approaches that are valuable and different from the conventional ones. Creativity requires an open environment that encourages students to experiment. Various factors are important for developing creativity, such as intrinsic motivation, diverse experience, support and inspiration from others. The teacher must use methods contributing to this process, such as brainstorming, association diagrams, constant creative search and analysis of its results, and active communication and discussion. Constant practice and curiosity also stimulate the development of creativity in students.

Creativity can also be seen as the ability to create innovative ideas or solutions. The development of creativity depends on several key factors, such as intrinsic

motivation, experience, cultural environment, and the influence of external factors. The learning process, in which creativity is important, should focus on constant experimentation. In the case of interface design in Figma, experimentation can be focused on selecting colour schemes, working with styles, selecting font pairs and graphic images, and developing system designs.

Creativity is developed by stimulating the thought process, which includes freedom of imagination and openness to new ideas. Stimulating methods, such as brainstorming and interdisciplinary collaboration, also contribute to the development of creativity [12].

In scientific works, creativity is defined as a key competence that includes the ability to generate new ideas, think innovatively and adapt to rapid change. Creativity is seen not only as a skill but also as a process that requires certain conditions for its development. It is an integral part of modern education that allows students to respond effectively to labour market challenges and be competitive [12].

Creativity is the step-by-step development of an idea that takes place in favourable conditions that stimulate innovative thinking, and providing such conditions is extremely important in the educational process. Practical tasks and activities, such as discussions and group work, that promote the development of creative thinking are necessary. It is also important to create an environment where students can freely express their ideas, experiment, and improve their collaboration and critical thinking skills, which are important elements of the creative process.

The key to fostering creativity is an environment fostering divergent thinking, including flexibility, originality, idea generation, and evaluation skills. Among the methods for stimulating creativity are active discus-

sion, where non-standard ideas are encouraged, associative thinking, and combining different ideas. The creative process has four main stages: preparation, incubation, insight, and verification. To support creativity, methods such as brainstorming and creating an environment that facilitates the free exchange of ideas are important [13].

The development of creativity depends on several key factors, such as intrinsic motivation, experience, cultural environment, and active immersion in new contexts to stimulate creative thinking. A learning process that supports experimentation and tolerance for mistakes also contributes to the development of creativity [12].

In the Computer Graphics and Graphical Interface Design course, students are encouraged to use their imagination and be open to new ideas. Methods such as experimenting with graphic styles and design systems in Figma, preceded by a constant creative search for references, support the development of creativity in the classroom. Each student's work on their project creates the conditions for experimentation.

Within their academic groups, students, with the teacher's help, create an environment that encourages innovation and accepts the possibility of mistakes as part of the process. In practical classes, one of the activities is brainstorming, and the final stage of the work is the presentation and active discussion of students' projects. It is worth noting that the course curriculum provides for interdisciplinary cooperation, which helps to use knowledge from other disciplines in the project, which also has a positive impact on the formation of creativity. Namely, the use of skills with raster and vector graphic editors, with the choice of editors left to students. In their independent creative search, students must determine for what purposes a particular graphic editor is preferable.

In the Computer Graphics and GUI Design course, the study of topics begins with introducing students to the basic principles of computer graphics, including the differences between raster and vector graphics. Students learn to work with different file formats (JPEG, PNG, SVG, etc.) and their advantages and limitations. Considerable attention is also paid to the basics of typography, colour theory and composition, allowing future designers to create visually appealing and functional interfaces effectively. After the theoretical part, students get acquainted with the essential tools of Figma and learn its interface and basic functions for

working with graphics so they can use the editor successfully in their future work.

An important stage in preparing for interface design is the assignment aimed at introducing the principles of user analysis, which helps to identify the needs and expectations of the target audience. Students learn how to create user personas to represent typical product users. In addition, students conduct competitor analysis, researching existing solutions and identifying the strengths and weaknesses of similar products. They formulate interface requirements for the following design stages based on the data obtained. Students are also introduced to concepts such as hierarchy of elements, ease of navigation, and minimalism. The practical block focuses on creating lo-fi layouts in Figma, allowing you to develop sketches quickly without detailed elaboration. Students also learn how to create User Flow scenarios, which helps them understand user interaction logic with the interface. Practical tasks using Figma aim to develop creative approaches to building information architecture and wireframe development.

The development of adaptive layouts allows students to work on their grid skills to ensure a structured arrangement of elements. Particular attention is paid to optimising interface components for different screens, contributing to the user experience, and working on User Flow in Figma.

Students will learn to create interactive prototypes in Figma, adding animations and transitions between screens. The course also covers prototype presentation techniques, where students demonstrate the functionality of their projects.

The last topic is dedicated to preparing students to present their projects. Students justify their design decisions by explaining the choice of interface, colour scheme, and user experience elements. They also demonstrate interactive transitions and the functionality of their apps.

The process of studying computer graphics and graphic interface design aims to develop not only professional competencies but also soft skills. During the course, each student develops their project in stages. Conducting research during the course, including competitor analysis, audience research, collecting references, and constant discussion of the group results, helps foster creativity.

Students present the results of this type of research in the form of creatives prepared in the Figma cloud design service (see Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Fragment of a presentation by a student of the speciality 122 'Computer Science', created in Figma
Source: Author's elaboration

Students majoring in Computer Science 122 are encouraged to develop their creativity through tasks aimed at creative search, generalisation of the materials obtained by researching existing solutions in the field of interface design, brainstorming, and teamwork.

Thanks to such opportunities, Figma contributes to the development of soft skills. Students learn to generate new ideas, adapt to changes and make creative decisions, which are key soft skills for successful work in the IT field. In addition, this tool allows them to immerse themselves in real-world working conditions, as Figma is widely used in professional environments to create interfaces for web and mobile applications and games.

Overall, using Figma in the educational process positively impacts students' preparation to work on real projects after graduation and helps foster creativity in students. However, in addition to the learning environment organised by the teacher during the study of the discipline, it is also worth considering the individual characteristics of students that affect the process of creativity development. Individual factors include personality traits such as curiosity, divergent thinking, and intrinsic motivation. Motivation plays a key role, where intrinsic motivation (interest in the activity) contributes to greater creativity than extrinsic motivation (e.g. rewards). External factors include a supportive environment where innovation is encouraged and the opportunity to interact with different ideas and people. The cultural context is also important, as it either stimulates or restricts creativity [13].

We experimented with investigating the impact of the Figma cloud design service on developing students' creativity. Computer Graphics and Graphical Interface

Design were taught to three groups of 2nd year IT students. During eight labs, students worked on building and testing their projects. The input task for the experiment was to create and present four computer graphics works. At the end of the course, students were assigned to create presentation materials for the project that they had been working on during the course. While studying Figma and the basics of building interfaces, students were offered the following practices: open-ended tasks (students chose the form of execution), brainstorming, researching real cases in the field of graphical interfaces, and completing tasks in a team. The teacher's observation and evaluation of the results of the course's opening and final assignments were based on the following criteria: originality, flexibility, productivity, and detail. At the beginning of the course, the level of originality of student work was average, with a predominance of standard solutions. After using Figma and applying methods that influence the formation of creativity, there was a significant increase in the uniqueness of approaches to solving problems. About 78% of students submitted final papers with elements of novelty that distinguished them from others. Thanks to team practices and brainstorming sessions, students became more flexible in problem-solving. In the final projects, most works demonstrated diverse solutions, demonstrating the student's ability to adapt to changes and combine different ideas.

To test the effectiveness of using Figma to develop creativity in the educational process, 65 and 65 students (control group (CG) and experimental group (EG)) were included in the experiment.

In the experimental groups, students were taught using Figma, while in the control groups, they were taught using standard tools.

The levels of creativity were determined based on testing within the discipline of Computer Graphics and Graphical Interface Design.

Table 1 and Figure 3 show comparative statistical data before and after the experiment in the EG and CG, respectively.

Table 1.

Comparative distribution of CG and EG students by level of academic achievement at the beginning and end of the pedagogical experiment

The level of educational achievement	Before		After	
	CG	EG	CG	EG
Primary (1-59)	8	7	7	5
Intermediate (60-73)	30	31	28	22
Sufficient (74-89)	21	22	23	26
High (90-100)	6	5	7	12
Sum	65	65	65	65

Fig. 3. Comparative distribution of students in CG and EG by level of academic achievement at the beginning and end of the pedagogical experiment

Source: Own research

At the beginning of the pedagogical experiment, Pearson's χ^2 test was used to test the statistical equivalence of EG and CG, which revealed that the samples did not have statistically significant differences (since $\chi^2_{emp} = 0.35$, $\chi^2_{emp} < \chi^2_{0.05}$). Therefore, we can assume equal conditions in the EG and CG. At the end of the experiment, positive dynamics of sufficient and high levels of academic achievement in the experimental group were revealed, which also led to Pearson's χ^2 test application. The result of this test showed that the samples have statistically significant differences at this stage since $\chi^2_{emp} = 8.52$, $\chi^2_{emp} > \chi^2_{0.01}$.

The experiment showed that the Figma cloud service is an effective tool for developing students' creativity. Practical tasks involving the use of Figma tools, teamwork, brainstorming, and analysis of real-life cases provided a better approach to learning and contributed to the development of original thinking. The growth in all evaluation criteria confirms the feasibility of using Figma in the educational process.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that the use of Figma in the process of training bachelors in the field affects the formation of creativity and important professional skills in students in the field

of information technology. Thanks to Figma's functionality, including interactivity, teamwork support, and access to an extensive library of components and plugins, plugins can design graphical interfaces for various digital products in a real-world environment. This experience helps develop soft skills such as creative and critical thinking, generating new ideas, and working effectively in a team.

The introduction of Figma into the educational process positively impacts students' readiness to work on real projects after graduation. Thus, using modern tools such as Figma is an important component of training highly qualified professionals who can successfully meet the challenges of the modern labour market, promote innovation in the IT sector, and creatively approach complex professional tasks.

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